

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF ATTENUATION CORRECTION IN PERFUSION SCINTIGRAPHY OF MYOCARD

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cardiac single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) is one such technique that has a potential to overcome the limitations of conventional myocardial SPECT including the absolute quantification. Despite the progress in the field of medical technology, soft tissue attenuation is still a hindrance in the path of the diagnostic accuracy of myocardial perfusion imaging. Soft tissue attenuation artefacts are more likely to occur in patients with high body mass index (BMI) undergoing myocardial perfusion imaging (MPI) and therefore it is routine practice to perform attenuation correction in this group of patients. However, that attenuation artefacts may also occur in patients with normal BMI. Soft tissue photon attenuation produces inhomogeneous defects that decrease the specificity of the test, thereby making it difficult to distinguish between coronary artery disease and the attenuation artifact.

Aim: The aim is to demonstrate the benefit of the use of CT and the attenuation correction in MPI.

Materials and Methods: This paper is a non-experimental (qualitative) research, that is, a scientific review of the literature. Upon creating their professional work, different databases were used, including Pub Med, Medline.

Results: The results we analyzed in this paper were collected from published academic journals.

Conclusion: Conclusions are concerning the aim of the research.

KEYWORDS attenuation corrections, MPI, artifacts, SPECT/CT

Introduction

Diseases of the myocardium are common, and they represent the number one medical burdens patients experience in the modern world, with the rise of obesity and diabetes rates. Many techniques have been developed to aid identification of myocardial condition, as well as pre-scan patients with risk factors such as obesity. Nuclear cardiology has not witnessed the development of new tracers or hardware in years. Hence there is a need for the development of improvised techniques [1].

Cardiac single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) is one such technique that has the potential to overcome the limitations of conventional myocardial SPECT including the absolute quantification. Despite the progress in the field of medical technology, soft tissue attenuation is still a hindrance in the path of the diagnostic accuracy of myocardial perfusion imaging [2].

Soft tissue attenuation artefacts are more likely to occur in patients with high body mass index (BMI) undergoing myocardial perfusion imaging (MPI), and therefore it is routine practice to perform attenuation correction in this group of patients [3].

However, attenuation artefacts may also occur in patients with normal BMI. Soft tissue photon attenuation produces inhomogeneous defects that decrease the specificity of the test, thereby making it difficult to distinguish between coronary artery disease and the attenuation artefact. This may lead to predominant increase in false positive studies. Diaphragmatic

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attenuation and breast attenuation are the most commonly documented artifacts. In obese persons lateral wall artifacts may also be noted. The worth of myocardial perfusion imaging (MPI) is indisputable. It is not only useful in the diagnosis of coronary artery disease (CAD) but also helps in risk stratification and management of patients with known or suspected CAD [4].

Myocardial perfusion imaging — CT based attenuation correction

Myocardial perfusion imaging (MPI), using ^{201}Tl and $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ labelled radiopharmaceuticals for stress/rest SPECT studies are at present the primary non-invasive modality for evaluation of coronary artery disease [5]. Its accuracy is, however, limited by image artefacts that can cause false-positive perfusion defects and therefore reduce the test specificity. Although the initial validation of MPI-SPECT performed in luminary sites reported specificity of greater than 90%, further large-scale clinical use of the technique has been associated with specificity in the range of 60% or lower [6, 7]. One of the most common image artefacts is caused by non-uniform reduction of photon activity from attenuation by soft tissue. This can be recognized, or at least suspected by experienced readers, because of the typical location and shape relative to the heart. Attenuation artefacts usually occur in the anterior wall in women with large breasts and the inferior wall in obese men [8, 9]. Although the true prevalence of soft tissue artefacts is unknown, estimates range between 20% and 50% of patients [10, 11].

Several approaches have been used to address the issue of spurious false-positive results in MPI due to photon attenuation including, among other options, awareness of their potential occurrence and location, routine assessment of raw imaging data, comparative evaluation of studies performed following a change in the patient's position (prone versus supine) and gated imaging which assesses wall motion. These approaches improve artefact recognition, but they all have limitations. Although guidelines of the American Society of Nuclear Cardiology recommend that attenuation correction should be performed in all patients, there are some patient populations that benefit more from this procedure, generally the largest-size patients. Depending on equipment availability and daily workload, the rest SPECT study is used in some centres as the criterion for triage decisions for performing attenuation correction acquisition.[12]

To determine the true radiotracer distribution in the myocardium, several techniques have been developed to generate patient-specific attenuation maps. Attenuation maps generated by transmission sources at the time of the scan have, until the last decade, been the most commonly used method of correction. Various transmission geometries have been adopted, including sheet, multiple lines, or scanning line sources, a fixed source positioned at the focal line of a fan-beam collimator, or a moving point source [13].

Cardiac SPECT is performed using a dual-head gamma camera equipped with low energy, high-resolution parallel hole collimators, and with the detectors at 90° to each other. The acquisition is performed over a 180° orbit during a period of 12–20 minutes. Dual isotopes acquisition uses ^{201}Tl for rest and $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -sestamibi or $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -tetrofosmin for stress, while single isotope acquisition uses the same isotope, $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -sestamibi or $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -tetrofosmin for both rest and stress. For ^{201}Tl , imaging energy windows of 30% and 20% for the 70 keV and 167 keV peaks, respectively, are used, while the energy window width for $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ is 20% for the 149 keV peak. Both the rest and stress

SPECT studies are followed by a low-dose CT (20–30 mAs, 140 keV for the diagnostic CT, or 2.5 mAs, 140 keV for a camera-mounted CT), which is used for photon attenuation correction of the scintigraphic data. The CT-attenuation correction study is performed only over the area of the heart, as defined by the operator. The patient is asked not to move during study progression to obtain good co-registration between the emission and the transmission scans [14].

Aim

The aim is to demonstrate the benefit of the use of CT and the attenuation correction in MPI.

Materials and Methods

This paper is a non-experimental (qualitative) research, that is, a scientific review of the literature. Upon creating their professional work, different databases were used, including Pub Med, Medline, using key words "attenuation corrections", "MPI", "artefacts", "SPECT / CT". The research is limited to articles published in English.

Results

They are demonstrated in the Table 1.

Table 1 Variables are relative to the objective of the research.

Author	Study name	Aim	Research method	Results
Huang R, Li F, Zhao Z, Liu B, Ou X, Tian R, Li L. (2011.)	Hybrid SPECT/CT for attenuation correction of stress myocardial perfusion imaging.	This study aimed to determine whether attenuation correction using the Hybrid SPECT/CT reduced attenuation artefacts.	Ninety-nine patients (55 men and 44 women) underwent coronary angiography and electrocardiography gated stress/rest myocardial perfusion imaging using Tc-99m sestamibi (MIBI) with CT-attenuation correction (CT-AC) for stress scans. Visual semi-quantitative analysis of the CT-AC and noncorrected perfusion images was performed.	The overall specificity, sensitivity, and accuracy for noncorrected versus CT-AC were 62.9% versus 79.0% (P = 0.041), 94.6% versus 91.9% (P = NS), and 74.7% versus 83.8% (P = 0.035), respectively. CT-AC increased specificity in the right coronary artery region, from 77.9% to 98.7% (P = 0.000), accompanied by a decrease in specificity in the left anterior descending region, from 94.1% to 82.4% (P = 0.008). CT-AC significantly reduced defect scores in the inferior wall. This was more obvious in men than in women (P = 0.027). In the anterior wall, although a tendency for defect scores to increase with CT-AC was observed only in men, no significant difference was found between the gender (P = 0.049).
Giubbini R.M, Gabanelli S, Lucchini S, Merli G, Puta E, Rodella C, Motta F, Paghera B, Rossini P, Terzi A, Bertagna F. (2011.)	The value of attenuation correction by hybrid SPECT/CT imaging on infarct size quantification in male patients with previous inferior myocardial infarct.	This study aimed to evaluate the value of AC for the assessment of infarct size in coronary artery disease patients after inferior myocardial infarction.	Gated-SPECT with Tc-labeled compounds with AC by hybrid SPECT/computed tomography (CT) was performed in 56 male patients with documented previous inferior myocardial infarction. Both corrected, and uncorrected SPECT images were processed after motion and scatter correction by ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction. When needed, a manual realignment between SPECT and computed tomography (CT) sections was performed. Uncorrected and corrected SPECT images were analyzed for perfusion using a 5-point segmental scoring scale from 0 (normal) to 4 (absent). Summed stress score (SSS), summed rest score (SRS), and summed difference score (SDS) of the inferior left ventricle wall (inferoseptal, inferior, infero-apical and inferolateral segments) were determined and compared with the regional wall motion score as determined by uncorrected gated-SPECT.	The SSS, SRS, SDS for attenuation-uncorrected and attenuation-corrected studies were 14.02 ± 7.9 , 9.51 ± 7 , 4.5 ± 3.2 and 9.39 ± 7.1 , 5.6 ± 6.1 , 3.8 ± 2.8 , respectively. Differences were statistically significant (P<0.0001) for SSS and SRS but not for SDS. The regional summed rest score of the inferior wall (SRS of inferior segments) showed a better correlation with the regional summed wall motion score of the same segments: $R^2=0.50$ in comparison to uncorrected SRS, $R^2=0.46$

<p>Płachcińska A, Włodarczyk M, Kovacevic-Kuśmierk K, Bieńkiewicz M, Drożdż J, Chiziński K, Kasprzak JD, Peruga JZ, Kuśmierk J. (2016.)</p>	<p>Diagnostic performance of myocardial perfusion single-photon emission computed tomography with attenuation correction.</p>	<p>To evaluate whether visual, semi-quantitative analysis of attenuation-corrected myocardial perfusion imaging provides an advantage over a non-corrected study.</p>	<p>A retrospective study applying AC was performed in 107 patients who had coronary angiography within three months. Patients underwent a stress/rest Tc-99m methoxyisobutylisonitrile (MIBI, POLATOM) double day SPECT/CT myocardial perfusion imaging. Images were analysed by two experienced nuclear medicine specialists (a consensus) applying a semiquantitative visual method. Coronary angiography findings were used as a reference for the analysis of diagnostic performance of myocardial perfusion study protocols.</p>	<p>AC increased the specificity of detection of CAD in the whole group of patients from 63% to 86% ($p = 0.0005$), with a slight reduction in sensitivity (from 83% to 79%). The improved specificity was also noted in the subgroups of male and female patients. Accuracy in the whole group of patients increased from 71% to 83% ($p = 0.01$). AC improved the specificity and accuracy of the method in the detection of perfusion defects in the right coronary artery (RCA) area from 73% to 88% ($p = 0.005$) and from 74% to 83% ($p = 0.04$), respectively, and the accuracy of the method in the left anterior descending (LAD) artery area from 79% to 87% ($p = 0.043$). It also reduced the number of ambiguous results of the study.</p>
<p>Ou X, Jiang L, Huang R, Li F, Zhao Z, Li L. (2013.)</p>	<p>Computed tomography attenuation correction improves the risk stratification accuracy of myocardial perfusion imaging.</p>	<p>We evaluated the prognostic value of single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) myocardial perfusion imaging with CT-AC.</p>	<p>Technetium-99m sestamibi stress/rest myocardial perfusion imaging was performed with SPECT and CT-AC in 935 patients. Images without and with AC were rated using the summed stress score (SSS) and classified as normal (SSS, 0-3), mildly abnormal (SSS, 4-8), or moderately or severely abnormal (SSS>8). All patients were followed up for a significant adverse cardiac event (MACE).</p>	<p>At the end of a mean follow-up period of 2.2 ± 0.8 years, there had occurred 42 MACEs [17 all-cause deaths (2%) and 25 nonfatal myocardial infarctions (3%)]. The annual frequency of MACEs in patients with normal SSS was 0.5% that in patients with mildly abnormal SSS was 2%, and in patients with moderately or severely abnormal SSS was 8%. With AC, more studies were categorized as definitely normal, and the number of patients with moderately to severely abnormal perfusion on CT-AC was reduced ($\kappa=0.32$, $P \leq 0.001$). The annual frequency of MACEs was similar between studies without AC and those with CT-AC for patients with normal or mildly abnormal SSS, whereas for the moderately to severely abnormal group the annual frequency increased significantly after CT-AC (4.5 vs 8.1%, $P=0.03$). Cumulative survival without MACE was highest among patients who had normal CT-AC studies (SSS<4) and was the least among patients who had moderately to severely abnormal studies (SSS>8; $P \leq 0.01$).</p>

<p>Shawgi M, Tonge CM, Lawson RS, Muthu S, James J, Arumugam P. (2012.)</p>	<p>Attenuation correction of myocardial perfusion SPET in patients of normal body mass index.</p>	<p>Soft tissue attenuation artefacts are more likely to occur in patients with high body mass index (BMI) undergoing myocardial perfusion imaging (MPI)</p>	<p>We collected data prospectively on 57 patients with BMI less than 25kg/m² who underwent stress-rest MPI single-photon emission tomography (SPET) as part of their standard management at our institution. The differences between the attenuation corrected (AC) and non-attenuation corrected (NC) images were evaluated by two experienced readers blinded to patient gender and clinical details.</p>	<p>Visual improvement in perfusion with attenuation correction was seen in 54.4% of patients with normal BMI and was more common in males (84.2%) than females (39.5%). Discordances between AC and NC were most frequent in the inferior, inferolateral and anteroseptal segments in both males and females and were also seen in the apical and anterior segments in some patients, mainly in females, in keeping with the well-recognized distribution pattern for attenuation artefacts.</p>
<p>Peli A, Camoni L, Zilioli V, Durmo R, Bonacina M, Bertagna F, Paghera B, Giubbini R. (2018.)</p>	<p>Attenuation correction in myocardial perfusion imaging affects the assessment of infarct size in women with previous inferior infarct.</p>	<p>This study aims to evaluate the role of AC in the assessment of infarct size in female patients with a history of myocardial inferior infarct.</p>	<p>We studied a population of 66 consecutive women, with a history of previous inferior myocardial infarct, by SPECT/computed tomography (CT) with 370+370 MBq of technetium-99m labelled compounds by a 2-day stress-rest protocol. Both AC and uncorrected gated-SPECT/CT studies were reconstructed after scatter and motion correction by ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction and resolution recovery. The coregistration of the transmission and emission scans was verified for all patients; any misalignment was realigned manually. Uncorrected and corrected SPECT images were analyzed by software QPS/QGS package using a 17-segment model. For each segment, perfusion and wall motion were quantified using a five-point score according to the American Society of Nuclear Cardiology guidelines. Summed stress, summed rest score (SRS), and summed difference score of the inferior left ventricle wall (inferior, inferoseptal, inferolateral, and apical inferior segments) were calculated. A linear correlation was used to assess the relationship between perfusion and the regional wall motion score as determined by uncorrected gated-SPECT.</p>	<p>The results of quantitative analysis of non-AC and CT-AC SPECT images, respectively, were as follows: summed stress score: 9.47±5.01 and 6.58±4.77% (P<0.001); SRS was 6.05±5.02 and 4.14±4.12% (P<0.001); the summed difference score was 2.92±2.74 and 2.52±2.63% (P=NS), respectively. The correlation between corrected and uncorrected SRS and the regional summed wall motion score of the same segment was R=0.31 versus R=0.34.</p>

<p>Mohseni M, Faghihi R, Haghigatafshar M, Entezarmahdi SM. (2018.)</p>	<p>Effects of the attenuation correction and reconstruction method parameters on conventional cardiac dynamic SPECT.</p>	<p>The main goal of this study is to evaluate the effect of attenuation correction (AC) on the estimation of the washout parameters extracted from dynamic SPECT using a conventional protocol</p>	<p>A physical phantom was employed to physically simulate the dynamic behaviour of a heart in the thorax. Using a dual detector SPECT system, 180° tomographic data in every 90seconds were acquired. The SPECT data were reconstructed using ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) method while different iterations and a Butterworth filter with different cut-off frequencies were applied. Estimated washout parameter of the time-activity curves (TACs) was compared with applying AC or without it</p>	<p>Results show that AC can improve the bias of computed washout parameter in normal regions (average bias reduction in normal ROI: 7%). Moreover, the post-reconstruction filtering and reducing the number of iterations in reconstructing phase can reduce the variance of the computed washout values in normal regions (from 3.99% for cut-off frequency 0.5cycle/cm and 32 times update in OSEM to 2.05% for cut-off frequency 0.35cycle/cm and 16 times update in OSEM). They also reduce the actual size of the defect region (13% reduction in defect extent for above change in reconstruction parameters).According to the results, the AC and postprocessing filtration can directly affect the standard deviation of washout value acquired by cardiac dynamic SPECT. These parameters also showed a direct effect on the defect extent in final results.</p>
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Conclusion

- Attenuation correction using Hybrid SPECT/CT improved specificity in the right coronary artery but decreased specificity in the left anterior descending. This technique is likely to be more useful in men than in women.[15]
- The combination of diaphragmatic attenuation and inferior myocardial infarction determines an artifactual overestimation of infarct size of inferior infarcts. The AC regional perfusion score (SRS) correlates with the regional wall motion score of the inferior wall. AC does not affect the detection and size of residual ischemia (SDS).[16]
- AC improved the diagnostic performance of myocardial perfusion study in the detection of CAD and identification of critically stenosed LAD and RCA vessels, with enhanced comfort of study interpretation.[17]
- CT-AC allows improved risk stratification for MACEs because there is a more clear separation between low risk and moderately to severely abnormal findings.[18]
- In conclusion, although small sample size was used in this study, changes in appearance with attenuation correction likely to represent attenuation artefacts were seen in 54.4% of patients with normal BMI and were two times more common in males than females. These changes were felt to be clinically relevant in that they could lead to a change in the final report and may ultimately affect the diagnosis and clinical management. Thus, attenuation correction could be of value in patients of normal BMI. Further larger studies with correlation with clinical follow-up or invasive coronary angiography are warranted.[19]
- In the female population, like in men, attenuation artefacts affect the calculation of the infarct size of the inferior wall, with overestimation of the infarct size in uncorrected images. The AC regional perfusion score (SRS) better correlates with the regional wall motion score of the inferior wall in women with previous inferior infarct.[20]
- The study showed that the AC may partly improve the bias of calculated normal washout value. The effect of attenuation correction on the defective washout value could not be answered comprehensively in this paper.[21]

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the authors of this study.

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